
Research

Research on the Impact of Digital Inclusive Finance on Green Technology Innovation

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Abstract: Green innovation is essential for supporting economic transitions, restructuring the economy, and fostering sustainable, consistent growth. The adoption of growth methods driven by green innovation is primarily reliant on the technical developments produced by organisations. Green inclusive finance, a combination of conventional finance and digital technology, is crucial for the progress of technological innovation. This article examines the field of green inclusive finance and the invention of green technology in enterprises. At first, a thorough analysis was conducted on three types of literature: green inclusive finance, green technology innovation, and the relationship between them. This article gives precise definitions for important topics such as green inclusive finance, green technological innovation, and financing restrictions by referring to relevant literature. Moreover, unlike other studies, this study considers the notion of financing restrictions when analysing the impact of green inclusive finance on business innovation. Additionally, it examines the role of finance limitations as an intermediary factor in this association.

Keywords: Financing constraints; Green inclusive finance; Green technology innovation

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Introduction

Green innovation development has emerged as a strategic objective and focus for the government in recent years. In light of the Middle East's economy progressing towards a phase of high-quality development and the ongoing advancement of supply side structural reform, it is crucial for enterprises to prioritise and actively execute green innovation strategies from a strategic standpoint. Enterprises play a significant role in driving green transformation and upgrading.

The government work report has incorporated the concept of the green economy. Green innovation will spearhead future economic development as a novel approach to productivity, manufacturing, and lifestyle. Within this policy framework, the focus is on how to stimulate the development of environmentally friendly technologies and improve the competitive advantage of businesses in the green sector. This will contribute to long-term growth in both social and economic aspects, making it a widely discussed subject. The objective of green technology innovation is to improve the competitive advantage of firms in the green sector, facilitate the transformation of the economy's structure, and attain

economic development of high quality. Green innovation has a crucial role in driving the execution of national policies, facilitating industrial advancement, and attaining sustainable development.

The 2014 Global Development Report defined inclusive finance as the provision of sustainable and efficient financial services to both institutions and individuals, catering to their requirements for transactions, savings, payments, and more. Xing Lecheng (2018) conducted a detailed analysis of the theoretical development and conceptual evolution of inclusive finance, focusing on commercial finance. He argued that the key concepts of inclusive finance are the "three service principles" and the "three can principles". The ongoing advancement and utilisation of big data and Internet technology can empower traditional financial institutions that depend on physical branches to overcome the limitations of time and space, and expand the reach of their financial products and services (Liang Shuanglu et al., 2019). Furthermore, the service is both convenient and efficient. Digital technology has revolutionised conventional companies by transitioning them from offline to online platforms. Leveraging artificial intelligence technology, it efficiently delivers easy and rapid services (Xie Xuanli et al., 2018). Furthermore, the level of control over hazards is higher. The conventional risk management approach, which relies on information backtracking, involves complex processes, expensive implementation, and is particularly vulnerable to limitations in time and space.

When it comes to assessing green inclusive finance, there are disparities in its progress at both national and global levels. According to Beck et al. (2007), the effectiveness and reach of financial services are strongly linked to the amount of development of inclusive finance. Thus, a total of eight indicators are suggested to gauge the level of inclusive finance development, derived from these two dimensions. These indicators encompass the quantity of deposits and loans, the quantity of ATMs, the quantity of financial institution branches, and the proportion of deposits and loans in the gross domestic product. Sarma (2008) developed a measuring method with a focus on banks. According to his perspective, the banking services industry is the primary tool to improve financial inclusivity.

The definition of green technological innovation presently lacks unanimity. The concept of green technological innovation was initially introduced by Braun et al. (1994) in 1994. Green technology innovation encompasses the technological advancements made by businesses in their production processes. This includes enhancing production methods, improving production technology, minimising pollutant emissions, recycling resources, and maximising efficiency. Tao Jianhong et al. (2004) argued that green technology innovation is a deliberate action taken to ensure the harmonious growth of the economy and the ecological environment, while minimising environmental harm through the creation of new technologies. Xie Li et al. (2016) devised a novel method to assess the innovation of green governance technology. They used the reciprocal of SO₂ intensity and the degree of pollutant reduction as the basis for their measurement. According to Li Wanhong et al. (2013), green technology innovation refers to the technical actions that prioritise enhancing energy efficiency within the research and development process.

2. Hypothesis Development

Green inclusive finance is an extension of inclusive finance that utilises digital technology to create innovative financial development forms. It maintains the fundamental characteristics of finance while introducing new elements in terms of both structure and content. The growth of the financial market facilitates the provision of financial services and products to businesses by addressing both the supply and demand of funds. This allows enterprises to overcome limitations caused by insufficient funds and promotes the successful execution of their innovation activities (Sheng Mingquan et al., 2021). The emerging business model of digital finance leverages the Internet as a platform to lower financial service costs by extensively analysing bank and enterprise data. This model enhances the efficiency of allocating financial resources, thereby offering ample financial support for enterprise research and innovation (Zhong Teng and Wang Changyun, 2017; Shen Minghao and Tan Weijie, 2022). Digital finance is a manifestation of technical innovation, encompassing state-of-the-art concepts and modern technology. The advancement will unavoidably result in the "butterfly effect" within the economy. Digital technology facilitates the collection and comparison of information between stagnant industries and industries with significant growth potential. This process brings market resources

closer to high-performing enterprises, eliminates stagnant industries, and speeds up the optimisation of resource allocation and industrial advancement. Thus, the capacity of green inclusive financing to foster technological innovation may directly enhance the industry and stimulate technical advancements in firms (Wu Qingtian and Zhu Yingxiao, 2021). Thus, this article presents hypothesis H1:

H1: Inclusive green finance can promote green technology innovation in enterprises.

Green technology innovation exhibits greater drawbacks in comparison to other technical advancements, including elevated expenses, protracted innovation cycles, and heightened risks. As a result, conventional financial institutions exercise caution when providing loans to businesses for green innovation initiatives, so creating challenges for organisations to secure finance from external sources and dampening their excitement for innovation. Green inclusive finance may utilise cutting-edge technologies like big data to reduce the barriers to financial services and expand funding options for businesses. Based on the categorization criteria for enterprise types, the Middle East categorises enterprises into two groups: major enterprises and small and medium-sized firms. Furthermore, green inclusive finance has the potential to decrease transaction costs, including those associated with information gathering, operational activities, and risk evaluation, so resulting in reduced financing expenses. Green inclusive finance is an emerging financial paradigm that use the Internet as its foundation. The fast progress of this development can diminish the reliance of financial services on physical brick-and-mortar establishments. Ultimately, digital finance may utilise advanced technologies like big data to streamline the transaction process, increase the visibility of information, reduce the imbalance of information between investors and financiers, and raise the efficiency of financing. The financial challenges encountered by small and medium-sized firms during their development process can be attributed to a variety of factors. Utilising digital finance may mitigate the imbalance of information and enhance the effectiveness of funding. Green inclusive finance addresses the financial limitations faced by firms in three specific areas, so encouraging their adoption of green technological innovation. To summarise, this article puts forward the hypothesis H2:

H2: Inclusive green finance promotes green technology innovation in enterprises by alleviating financing constraints.

3. Model Construction

1. Benchmark regression model

To test the impact of green finance on green technology innovation in enterprises, this article sets up the following model

$$\text{Patent}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Index}_{i,t} + \alpha_2 \sum \text{Controls}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{1}$$

In the above model, the subscript *i* denotes the enterprise, whereas *t* denotes the time. The dependent variable at the core is the patent, which serves as a representation of the extent of green technology innovation in firms. It is calculated by taking the natural logarithm of the total number of green invention patents applied for by these enterprises. The country's inclusive green finance index is the main variable of interest. The control variables consist of the asset return rate, enterprise size, audit opinion, and market index. The inclusion of individual fixed effects helps to address endogeneity issues. The random error term of the model is represented by the symbol $\varepsilon_{i,t}$. Stata 19.0 was utilised to evaluate Equation (1) Hausman. The findings indicate that this article employs a fixed effects model for regression analysis.

2. Mediated regression model

To test hypothesis 2, this article refers to the mediation effect testing procedure of Wen Zhonglin and Ye Baojuan (2014), and incorporates financing constraints (SA) into the analysis framework to test its mediation effect:

$$\text{Patent}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Index}_{i,t} + \alpha_2 \sum \text{Controls}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{2}$$

$$SA_{i,t} = b_0 + b_1 \text{Index}_{i,t} + b_2 \sum \text{Controls}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Patent}_{i,t} = c_0 + c_1 \text{Index}_{i,t} + c_2 SA_{i,t} + c_3 \sum \text{Controls}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{4}$$

In the given equation, the symbol $\sum$ denotes the control variable, the symbol $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ represents the random disturbance component, the symbol *i* represents the enterprise, and the symbol *t* indicates the year share. Equation (2) denotes that the value of 1 represents the overall influence of inclusive green finance on the advancement of green technology in

businesses. In equation (3), the value of 1 denotes the influence of inclusive green finance on the limitations faced by corporations in obtaining funding. In equation (4), the variable 1 represents the direct impact of inclusive green finance on the green technology innovation of enterprises, taking into account corporate financing constraints. The variable 2 represents the extent to which financing constraints influence the green technology innovation of enterprises, considering the presence of inclusive green finance. In the above equation, the value of 2 indicates the indirect impact of inclusive green finance on the innovation of green technology in firms. Specifically, it represents the intermediate effect caused by limits in funding.

4. Results and Analysis

1. Benchmark Regression

This article employs a fixed effects model for testing, as determined by the Hausman test findings. The regression findings in Table 1 demonstrate the simultaneous consideration of the impact consequences of three distinct characteristics of green inclusive finance.

Based on the empirical regression results presented in Table 1 (1), it is evident that the regression coefficient of Green inclusive finance (Index) is positively significant at the 5% level. Thus, hypothesis H1 has been confirmed, indicating that Green inclusive financing has the potential to stimulate business innovation. The reason for this is because digital finance may provide businesses a greater amount of cash via the use of digital technology. It also allows for the development of new financial goods and services, hence expanding the range of chances for different firms to access digital finance. Financial services provide significant advantages to businesses when they reach a certain minimum level. Enterprises may utilise the benefits of green inclusive financing to secure additional funding for research and development, hence fostering innovation in green technology.

The coefficient of coverage width in columns (2) to (3) of Table 5.4 is 0.362, and the coefficient of depth utilised is 0.365. These coefficients are statistically significant at the 5% and 1% levels, respectively, indicating a positive relationship. The digitalization degree coefficient in column (4) is 0.111, indicating a lack of statistical significance. Assuming that H1 has been verified or confirmed. Green inclusive finance employs methods that no longer depend on actual bank branches, which is why traditional financial systems represented by banks are no longer used. It facilitates the expansion of financial products and services to other locations and demographics, enabling firms to select diverse financing options for their funding needs. Amidst the growing adoption of environmentally-friendly and inclusive financial practices in several sectors, financial firms like insurance, payments, and monetary funds have also seen significant growth as they extend their range of services and products. During the digital transformation, financial institutions utilise tools like big data to gather data from banks and businesses. This improves information transparency, clarifies the financial requirements of businesses, and assists them in obtaining more substantial funding during the financing process. Consequently, it fosters the innovation of green technology within enterprises.

Table 1 Benchmark Regression Results Table

	(1) Patent	(2) Patent	(3) Patent	(4) Patent
Index	0.317** -1.972			
size	0.797*** -3.039	0.714*** -3.336	0.696*** -3.387	0.918*** -4.632
roa	-1.251* (-1.743)	-1.338 (-0.887)	-1.275 (-0.847)	-1.724 (-1.144)
opinion	-0.371 (-0.781)	-0.684 (-0.846)	-0.672 (-0.832)	-0.691 (-0.855)

lev	-2.207 (-1.053)	-1.538* (-1.833)	-1.552* (-1.854)	-1.704** (-2.038)
market	0.258 -1.592	0.24 -1.361	0.257 -1.58	0.415** -2.567
breadth		0.362** -2.533		
depth			0.365*** -2.994	
dig				0.111 -1.218
_cons	-18.167*** (-2.897)	-16.295*** (-3.391)	-16.160*** (-3.635)	-21.944*** (-5.167)
N	14150	14150	14150	14150
F	4.675	18.685	19.113	17.856

2. Mediation Effect Analysis

This article use the SA index as a means to assess funding limitations and utilises it as a mediator variable in order to do mediation effect regression. The equations utilised in this part are Equation (2), Equation (3), and Equation (4), and the outcomes of the regression analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Intermediary regression results

	(1) Patent	(2) SA	(3) Patent
Index	0.317* -1.872	0.003* -1.718	0.233* -1.659
size	0.797*** -3.039	1.187*** -228.028	-29.974* (-1.925)
roa	-1.251* (-1.743)	-0.011 (-0.933)	-0.972 (-1.360)
opinion	-0.371 (-0.781)	-0.002 (-0.089)	-0.331 (-0.574)
lev	-2.207 (-1.053)	-0.058*** (-5.055)	-0.71 (-0.505)
market	0.258 -1.592	0.001 -0.474	0.239 -1.535
SA			25.926* -1.951
_cons	-18.167*** (-2.897)	-22.339*** (-194.446)	560.988* -1.922
N	14150	14150	14150
F	4.675	2.641	4.423

Table 2 displays the regression findings for the relationship between green inclusive finance and corporate green technology innovation in column (1), and the relationship between green inclusive finance and the amount of corporate

financing limitations in column (2). Column (3) displays the impact of green inclusive funding on corporate green technological innovation, taking into account financing restrictions (SA) as a control variable in the regression analysis. The results table above shows that the coefficient (Index) of the Green inclusive finance Index in column (1) is 0.317, indicating that green inclusive finance promotes green technology innovation in enterprises with a significance level of 10%. In column (2), the coefficient of financing constraint (SA) for enterprises in the Digital Inclusive Gold category is 0.003, which is tested at a significance level of 10%. There is a clear correlation between the size of the green inclusive finance index and the extent of financing limitations experienced by businesses.

3. Robustness Test

Given the delayed effect of green inclusive financing on economic growth, this paper will employ the lagged explanatory variable as an instrumental variable. Furthermore, to enhance the reliability of the outcomes, the secondary index of green inclusive finance, namely the extent and comprehensiveness of coverage, was included as substitute variables to tackle the problem of endogeneity in the model. The findings are displayed in Table 3.

The L-Index in column (1) of Table 3 is 0.396, which is lower than the first period green inclusive finance index. By conducting a significance level test at a threshold of 5%, it has been demonstrated that even if there is a delay in the implementation of green inclusive financing, it may still effectively stimulate innovation in green technology inside firms. The L-breadth coefficient in column (2) is 0.433, while the L-depth coefficient utilised in column (3) is 0.425. Both coefficients pass the significance level test at 5%, suggesting that the breadth of digital coverage and the depth of usage contribute to the promotion of green technology innovation in firms. Thus, even accounting for endogeneity, the model's conclusions remain rather consistent, indicating the robustness of the findings from an alternative standpoint.

Table 3 Robustness Test

	-1	-2	-3	-4
	Patent	Patent	Patent	Patent
L.Index	0.396**			
	-2.229			
size	0.783***	0.766***	0.810***	0.996***
	-2.717	-2.631	-2.978	-3.648
roa	-1.622	-1.58	-1.61	-2.073
	(-0.853)	(-0.830)	(-0.849)	(-1.098)
Opinion	-0.312	-0.316	-0.291	-0.357
	(-0.265)	(-0.268)	(-0.246)	(-0.303)
lev	-2.474**	-2.460**	-2.576**	-2.616**
	(-2.219)	(-2.205)	(-2.323)	(-2.342)
market	0.265	0.243	0.24	0.448**
	-1.237	-1.111	-1.132	-2.342
L.breadth		0.433**		
		-2.269		
L.depth			0.425**	
			-2.498	
L.dig				0.126
				-1.167
_cons	-17.902***	-17.310***	-18.308***	-23.783***
	(-2.769)	(-2.626)	(-3.034)	(-4.072)
N	12735	12735	12735	12735

F	10.652	10.683	10.685	10.047
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5. Conclusion

As science and technology advance, the relationship between technology and money is becoming more interconnected. This has led to the emergence of a new financial model called green inclusive finance. Green inclusive finance has the potential to mitigate funding limitations and foster the development of green technological innovation in businesses, particularly in terms of its reach and extent of utilisation. Green technology innovation activities undertaken by organisations need adequate financial assurance, and they inherently exhibit traits such as prolonged length, elevated risk, and irreversibility, hence presenting challenges in securing external finance. Except for the impact of conventional finance, banks and other financial institutions incur significant expenses for corporate debt financing in order to guarantee credit safety. This often results in a limited number of financing options, challenges in securing funding, and elevated financing expenses. The influence of green inclusive finance on corporate innovation varies across different types of firms. More precisely, within the realm of green innovation, digital finance has a more pronounced and beneficial influence on high-tech firms and non-state-owned enterprises. However, its ability to drive non-high-tech enterprises and state-owned enterprises is either insignificant or minimal

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